

**A STUDY IMPACT OF STUDENT INITIATIVE MATERIAL
(SIM) AMONG STUDENTS WITH REFER IN
DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE,
PERAMBALUR**

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Abstract:

The instruments used were objectives test questions. College students were used, the control test and the experimental. The experimental College was tested one times, while the control test was tested once. The data collected were analyzed using simple percentage method. Students that was student initiative material practices performed better than those who are cooperation. Student initiative material generally leads to high improvement in student's academic performance. Based on these findings, it was recommended that qualified students should be best improving the academic result and a study on performance to developing colleges.

Key Words: Student Initiative Material, Learning Skills, Performances

Introduction:

There should be a reform in the classroom learning activity providing facilities for tutorials, group discussions, individual work, seminars, use of audio-visual aids etc., with a view to developing the skills needed by students in their future career. Academic writing is an important part of every curriculum whether you are in high school or you are a university student. The objective of all such study material is to see how better you can express yourself through words and how much you know about a subject. An study material is a task that someone is given to do, usually as part of their job.

An study is also a piece of academic work given to students. The project assignment is a compulsory part of the course and should be carried out by student groups. The results of this assignment contribute 50% of the final course score. It will therefore, require considerable efforts in time, input as well as critical thinking from each student. It is required that the student group will work independently throughout the project work including: information searching, literature study, data treatment /analysis, material compiling and the final reporting.

Student initiative material is the generic term used to describe the resources teachers used to deliver to instruction. Study material can support student learning and increase student success. Ideally, the study materials will be tailored to the content in which they're being used, to the students in whose class they are being used. Study materials come in many shapes and sizes, but they all have in common the ability to support student learning. This chapter presents the findings, of the study based, suitable pedagogic recommendations can be made. It makes necessary recommendations and suggestions to the text book writers and the teachers of English it also offers suggestions or further research in the field. The chapter also presents the summative statement and concludes the study.

Review of Literature:

Zeiger (2010) According to the results of the study of the U.S. Department of Education on "truancy", which is related to tardiness, being present and on time in going to Colleges are big factors on the "success and behavior" of the students. Thus, it is a lot important to value time and practice being on time while being a student.

Santillano (2010) stated that psychological theorists considered some "personality traits, including low self-esteem and anxiety" as triggering factors of tardiness. She also mentioned that while some theorists considered tardiness as an "inborn quality" since our being early or late is "partially biologically determined", which she also agreed, other experts also believed that some people are "chronically tardy" for the reason that they consciously and unconsciously get good things from it.

Moore and Smith (1962) studied the effectiveness of programmed instruction by machine, programmed text book, plus a weekly seminar vs. text book plus weekly seminar. No significant differences in achievement related to teaching machine, programmed text book or conventional text book were found. They also studied the effectiveness of the teaching machine, programmed text book, and conventional text book without supplementary class work. The machine group, scored significantly higher than the conventional text group both on immediate and delayed post-tests.

Objectives of the Study:

- A study impact of student initiative material (SIM) among students with reference in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.
- To support for the students developing their learning skills.
- To helps the students for their better performance using of student initiative material (SIM).
- To analysis the student to getting more marks in University Exam.

Needs and Importance of the Study:

- Student initiative materials are important because they significantly increase student achievement by supporting student learning.
- This process aids in the learning process by allowing the students to explore the knowledge independently as well as providing repetition.
- Study materials can also add important structure to lesson planning & the delivery of instruction.
- Study materials in teaching are crucial to the success of student achievement.

Scope of Study:

- This study developing their skills.
- This study analysing the better performance of the student.
- To Analyzes Student Performance Appraisal.
- The Methodology helpful for the Student who Concentrate on the Study.
- Evaluate the Knowledge Level of the Students

Research Design and Methodology:

The sources of data used in this project report is primary data

Primary Data:

Primary data consists of original information gathered from the sample size of 360 respondents.

Data Collection:

The data collection tool is used for the research in “Questionnaires” to get the primary data for the research

Research Design:

A research design is the set of methods and procedures used in collecting and analyzing measures of the variables specified in the problem research. The design of a study defines the study type and sub-type, research problem, hypotheses, independent and dependent variables, experimental design, and, if applicable, data collection methods and a statistical analysis plan. A research design is a framework that has been created to find answers to research questions.

Research Hypothesis:

A research hypothesis is a specific, clear, and testable proposition or predictive statement about the possible outcome of a scientific research study based on a particular property of a population, such as presumed differences between groups on a particular variable or relationships between variables.

Null Hypothesis:

A null hypothesis is a type of hypothesis used in statistics that proposes that there is no difference between certain characteristics of a population (or data-generating process).

Alternative Hypothesis:

An alternative hypothesis states that there is statistical significance between two variables.

Sample Size:

The sample size selected for the study is 360 students

1	Sampling Technique	Simple Random Sampling
2	Sample Size	360
3	Population	3216
4	Sample Area	Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur

Statistical Tools of the Study:

Collected data was analyzed with the help of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square Test
- Correlation
- Anova Test

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table Shows Student Initiative Material (SIM) Helpful for University Exam

S.No	Particulars	Percentage
1	Yes	82.5
2	No	5

3	Neutral	12.5
Total		100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The table shows that 82.5% of respondents are yes, 5% of the respondents are no and 12.5% of respondents are neutral.

Correlation Test:

Table Showing the Relationship between the Student Initiative Material (SIM) Helpful for Preparing University Exam and Student Initiative Material (SIM) Helpful For Maintaining Time Management

SIM Helpful for Preparing University Exam	297	18	45	360
SIM Helpful for Maintaining Time Management	333	6	21	360

Answer: $rx_y = 1.26$

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between the student initiative material (SIM) helpful for preparing university exam and student initiative material (SIM) helpful for maintaining time management.

Suggestion:

Most of respondents said that the college clearly defines the Student Initiative Material Practices it is help to perform the students better. Student Initiative Material Practices are agreeing the most of the students in the college. Most of the respondents said that easy to understand and improve the knowledge skills. Some of the respondents said that help to improve the Communication skill, writing skills. The college students should be provide adequate to extra instructions study. Student’s suggestions and feedback must be considered. Most of respondent’s students are feel disk suggestions for SIM Note Practices.

Conclusions:

It is very important, therefore, to maintain quality in designing the textbook. The following suggestions may be very useful in improving the (1) Before writing the text the course designers should identify the „needs“ and demands“ of the students. He should prepare a detailed profile of what the learner needs to be able to do in English based on which will be a specification of the language skills, functions, required to meet the specified needs. In the beginning of this chapter the significant findings of the study have been listed. The Continuous Assessment Practices use to Students Prepare University Exams, Improve your Creative Thinking, Changes on your Stage Fear, Writing Practices improve University Exams. So students are improving Learning Process and Interest on all subjects the skills Helpful for time management university exam, developing innovation Performance to Internals Marks, and Academic Results.

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